

DIBiMT: A Novel Benchmark for Measuring Word Sense Disambiguation Biases in Machine Translation

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Abstract

Lexical ambiguity poses one of the greatest challenges in the field of Machine Translation. Over the last few decades, multiple efforts have been undertaken to investigate incorrect translations caused by the polysemous nature of words. Within this body of research, some studies have posited that models pick up semantic biases existing in the training data, thus producing translation errors. In this paper, we present DIBiMT, the first entirely manually-curated evaluation benchmark which enables an extensive study of semantic biases in Machine Translation of nominal and verbal words in five different language combinations, namely, English and one or other of the following languages: Chinese, German, Italian, Russian and Spanish. Furthermore, we test state-of-the-art Machine Translation systems, both commercial and non-commercial ones, against our new test bed and provide a thorough statistical and linguistic analysis of the results. We release DIBiMT at <https://nlp.uniroma1.it/dibimt> as a closed benchmark with a public leaderboard.

1 Introduction

The polysemous nature of words poses a long-standing challenge in a wide range of Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks such as Word Sense Disambiguation (Navigli, 2009; Bevilacqua et al., 2021) (WSD), Information Retrieval (Krovetz and Croft, 1992) (IR) and Machine Translation (Emelin et al., 2020) (MT).

In MT, some research works have addressed the ability of systems to disambiguate polysemous words. For instance, given the sentence *He poured a shot of whiskey*, the polysemous target word *shot* unequivocally means *a small quantity* and therefore a possible translation into Italian could be: *Versò un goccio di whiskey*. However, some MT systems propose the following translation: *Versò uno sparo*

di whiskey in which the noun *sparo* means *gun-shot*. This is one of many examples that seem to encourage a deeper performance analysis in scenarios in which MT systems are required to deal with polysemous words and, specifically, with infrequent meanings of polysemous words. Although state-of-the-art MT systems, both commercial and non-commercial ones, achieve impressive BLEU scores on standard benchmarks, in our work we demonstrate that they still present significant limitations when dealing with infrequent word senses, which standard metrics fail to recognize.

In the last few decades, attempts have been made to investigate the aforementioned phenomena. In fact, recent studies have observed a direct correlation between semantic biases in the training data and semantic errors in translation. However, their findings are limited by the following shortcomings: i) they are not based on entirely manually-curated benchmarks; ii) they rely heavily on automatically-generated resources to determine the correctness of a translation; and iii) they do not cover multiple language combinations.

In this work, we address the aforementioned drawbacks and present DIBiMT, to the best of our knowledge the first fully manually-curated evaluation benchmark aimed at investigating the impact of semantic biases in MT in five language combinations, covering both nouns and verbs. This benchmark allows the community not only to better explore the described phenomena, but also to devise innovative MT systems which better deal with lexical ambiguity. Specifically, the contributions of the present work are threefold:

- We present DIBiMT, a novel gold-quality test bed for semantic biases in MT that goes beyond a simple accuracy score, covering five language combinations, namely English and one or other of the following languages: Chinese, German, Italian, Russian and Spanish;

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Figure 1: Example of an annotated dataset item. Target word is **shot**, in its meaning of a “small drink of liquor”. We expect translations to contain, for example in Italian, *goccio* (lit. a drop), but not, for example in Spanish, *pistolero* (a person who shoots).

- We define four novel metrics that better clarify the semantic biases within MT models;
- We provide a thorough statistical and linguistic analysis in which we compare 7 state-of-the-art MT systems, including both commercial and non-commercial ones, against our new benchmark. Furthermore, we extensively discuss the results.

To enable further research, we release DIBIMT as a closed benchmark with a public leaderboard at <https://nlp.uniroma1.it/dibimt>.

2 Related Work

Over the course of the last few decades, several approaches to the evaluation of the lexical choice in MT have been proposed. To this end, cross-lingual benchmarks were created in which systems were required to provide the translation or a substitute for a given target word in context in a target language (Vickrey et al., 2005; Mihalcea et al., 2010; Lefever and Hoste, 2013).

More recently, Gonzales et al. (2017) put forward ContraWSD, a dataset which includes 7,200 instances of lexical ambiguity for German → English, and 6,700 for German → French. This dataset pairs every reference translation with a set of contrastive examples which contain incorrect translations of a polysemous target word. For each instance, the answer provided by systems is considered correct if the reference translation is scored higher. Based on a denoised version of the ContraWSD dataset and focusing on the language combination German → English, Gonzales et al. (2018) present the Word Sense Disambiguation Test Suite which, unlike ContraWSD, evaluates MT output directly rather than by scoring translations. The suite consists of a collection of 3,249 sentence pairs in which the German source

sentences contain one ambiguous target word. As target words, the authors considered only words in German whose translation into English does not cover multiple senses, thus making the evaluation more straightforward. Despite their effectiveness, such benchmarks do not allow systems to be tested in multiple language combinations, and only cover a very limited number of words and senses. To address these limitations, Raganato et al. (2019) proposed MuCoW, an automatically-created test suite covering 16 language pairs, with more than 200,000 sentence pairs derived from word-aligned parallel corpora.

Other research studies investigated the disambiguation capabilities of MT systems by exploring their internal representations (Marvin and Koehn, 2018; Michel et al., 2019), or improving them via context-aware word embeddings (Liu et al., 2018). More recently, Emelin et al. (2020) introduced a statistical method for the identification of disambiguation errors in neural MT (NMT) and demonstrated that models capture data biases within the training corpora, which leads these models to produce incorrect translations. Although the authors expected their approach to be transferable to other language combinations, they only focused on German → English.

Based on the findings and open research questions raised in the aforementioned works, the present paper aims at investigating not only the presence, but also, most importantly, the nature and properties of semantic biases in MT in multiple language combinations, via a novel entirely manually-curated benchmark called DIBIMT and a thorough performance analysis.

3 Building DIBIMT

The DIBIMT benchmark focuses on detecting Word Sense Disambiguation biases in NMT, i.e., biases of certain words towards some of their more frequent meanings. The creation of such a dataset requires i) a set of unambiguous and grammatically-correct sentences containing a polysemous target word; ii) a set of correct and incorrect translations of each target word into the languages to be covered. Figure 1 depicts an example of a dataset item.

3.1 Preliminaries

BabelNet Similarly to previous studies, we rely on BabelNet¹ (Navigli et al., 2021), a large multilin-

¹<https://babelnet.org>

gual encyclopedic dictionary whose nodes are concepts represented by synsets, i.e., sets of synonyms, containing lexicalizations in multiple languages and coming from various heterogeneous resources, including, inter alia, WordNet (Miller et al., 1990) and Wiktionary.² Let us define \mathbb{B} as an abstraction used to query the subset of synsets in BabelNet that contain at least one sense³ from WordNet and one or more senses in languages other than English,⁴ while only considering senses coming from high-quality sources, i.e., language-specific wordnets.

Formal Notation Given an arbitrary synset σ , we define $\Lambda_L(\sigma)$ as the set of lexicalizations of σ in language L contained within \mathbb{B} . As an example, let us consider the synset $\tilde{\sigma}$ corresponding to the *drink* meaning of the word *shot*. $\tilde{\sigma}$ contains lexicalizations in different languages, including: *Shot_{DE}*, *shot_{EN}*, *nip_{EN}*, *chupito_{ES}*, *trago_{ES}*, *bicchierino_{IT}* and *goccio_{IT}*. Hence, $\Lambda_{EN}(\tilde{\sigma}) = \{\textit{shot}, \textit{nip}\}$, while $\Lambda_{ES}(\tilde{\sigma}) = \{\textit{chupito}, \textit{trago}\}$.

Furthermore, let λ_P represent a (lemma, part of speech) pair, where P is the part of speech. We denote $\Omega_L(\lambda_P) = \{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\}$ as the set of synsets which contain λ_P as a lexicalization in language L according to \mathbb{B} . Additionally, we define $\delta_L(\lambda_P) = |\Omega_L(\lambda_P)|$ as the polysemy degree, i.e., the number of senses, of λ_P in language L . For example, given $\lambda_P = \textit{shot}_{NOUN}$, $\Omega_{EN}(\lambda_P)$ would be the set of synsets associated with the nominal term *shot* (e.g., the act of firing, a photograph and a drink, among others).

3.2 Sentence Selection Process

In this section, we detail the creation process of our dataset, i.e., the selection of our sentences as well as the construction and filtering of our items.

Item Structure and Notation Before we proceed, let us formally state how each item in the dataset is structured: given a source sentence $s = [w_1, \dots, w_n]$ as a sequence of words, and given a target word⁵ w_i in s tagged with some synset σ , we consider $X = (s, w_i, \sigma)$ as an *initial item* of the dataset, i.e., an instance composed of

²<https://www.wiktionary.org/>

³A “sense” is a lexicalization of a specific synset in some language. Henceforth, we will refer to lexicalizations and senses interchangeably.

⁴Specifically, we consider synsets that have lexicalizations in English, Italian, German, Russian, Spanish and Chinese.

⁵For simplicity, we use the term *word* here, but our work focuses on multi-word expressions as well (both in source and target sentences).

an English sentence s , a target word w_i and its associated synset σ ; this instance can be annotated for candidate translations of w_i in some language L . We also denote λ_P^X as the (lemma, POS) pair of w_i .

3.2.1 Starting Sentence Pool

We collect our *initial items* from two main sources: WordNet and Wiktionary.⁶ Specifically, we use the examples from WordNet Tagged Glosses (Langone et al., 2004), where each sentence’s target word was manually associated with its synset⁷, thereby readily providing the first batch of *initial items*.

As for Wiktionary, instead, we start by obtaining every usage example s and its associated definition d (filtering out archaic usages and slang), then, we automatically extract the target words from the corresponding example.⁸ Now, the only step that remains in order to construct an *initial item* is to associate a synset σ with the word w_i used in the example s . We perform this association in two phases: first, we try to map the definition d related to the example s to a BabelNet synset by relying on the automatic mappings available in BabelNet 5 between WordNet and Wiktionary, discarding examples for which this association can not be found; second, we manually validate and correct these successful associations to ensure that our *initial items* are of high quality.

3.2.2 Sentence Filtering

We apply a filtering step to the original sentences in order to select examples that are likely to be more challenging for the models to translate: i) we discard every *initial item* X for which $\delta_{EN}(\lambda_P^X) < 3$, i.e., we retain only sentences whose associated (lemma, POS) pair has a polysemy degree of at least 3 in \mathbb{B}_{EN} ; ii) we retain at most only one sentence per sense per source⁹; iii) differently from previous works, which impose a strict requirement on synsets that are monosemous in the target language, we retain sentences satisfying the following requirement. Let us consider the nominal senses of the word *bank*: among them, one represents a specific aviation maneuver. In Italian, this synset

⁶We use the dump of September 2021.

⁷Which we convert from WordNet to BabelNet.

⁸In Wiktionary, target words are marked in bold inside the example sentence.

⁹The reasoning for this choice is twofold: on the one hand, oftentimes Wiktionary has multiple examples for the same synset, that differ in only one or two words, thus we skip them to avoid repetitions; on the other hand, we obtain an increase in sense coverage without worsening the annotator load.

includes one lexicalization, *avvitamento*; although this is not monosemous in Italian (e.g., *avvitamento* might also refer to a *screw thread*), neither of the other possible senses of *avvitamento* has *bank* as an English lexicalization, which, for Italian, satisfies our third condition. If the same holds true for all languages, the synset passes the test and thus the sentence is retained.

3.3 Annotating the Dataset

Once the set of *initial items* is ready, we can proceed with the annotation phase, which will produce our *annotated items*.

Specifically, given a language L and an *initial item* $X = (s, w_i, \sigma)$, we associate a set of good (\mathcal{G}_L) and bad (\mathcal{B}_L) translation candidates with X , which represent words that, respectively, we do, and do not, expect to see in a translation of sentence s in language L . Finally, we refer to X_L as an *annotated item*, i.e., the tuple $(s, w_i, \sigma, \mathcal{G}_L, \mathcal{B}_L)$.

3.3.1 Pre-annotation Item Creation

Before moving forward with the annotation phase, we pre-populate the sets of good (\mathcal{G}_L) and bad (\mathcal{B}_L) lexicalizations for a given *initial item* X in language L extracting them from \mathbb{B} . Formally, we assign $\mathcal{G}_L = \Lambda_L(\sigma)$, i.e., the set of lemmas in language L of the BabelNet synset associated with σ ; furthermore, we set $\mathcal{B}_L = \bigcup_{\hat{\sigma} \in \Omega_L(\lambda_{\mathbb{B}}^X) \setminus \{\sigma\}} \Lambda_L(\hat{\sigma})$, i.e., the set of all lemmas in language L of BabelNet synsets associated with any $\hat{\sigma}$ excluding σ . With this step, we produce an automatically populated version of our *annotated items*.

3.3.2 Annotation Guidelines

We instruct annotators to update the set of good (\mathcal{G}_L) and bad (\mathcal{B}_L) lexicalizations of $w_i \in s$ such that each lexicalization contained in the respective set can be considered a good or a bad translation equivalent for the target word in the provided sentential context.¹⁰

We also instruct annotators to discard sentences in which i) the target word w_i is an idiomatic expression or a proper noun, and ii) the semantic context is not sufficient to properly disambiguate w_i .

Given the expertise required to carry out this task, we rely on three highly qualified translators: one for Italian, German and Russian; one for Spanish and one for Chinese. Our annotators satisfy the

¹⁰Any lexicalization of σ in L that is removed from \mathcal{G}_L is automatically placed in \mathcal{B}_L .

	All	Nouns	Verbs
# items	597	314	286
# lemmas	305	186	147
# synsets	471	254	217

Table 1: General statistics of our annotated dataset. POS-specific lemmas do not sum to “All” as they can overlap across POS tags (e.g., run).

	%OG	%RG	%SL
DE	50.9	25.0	59.7
ES	49.6	19.5	47.7
IT	49.1	38.2	67.1
RU	67.4	57.3	54.4
ZH	55.2	69.0	46.3
Mean	54.4	41.8	55.0

Table 2: Annotation Statistics: %OG represents the average percentage of Good lemmas that are Original, i.e., were added by our annotators; %RG represents the average percentage of Good lemmas that were Removed, i.e., lemmas that came from BabelNet and that our annotators deemed incorrect in the context of the given example; %SL represents the average percentage of times two senses Share the same set of Lexicalizations for two different example sentences.

following requirements: they are native speakers or hold C2-level certifications and work as professional translators in the given language combinations. The full instructions provided to the annotators can be found in Appendix C.

3.3.3 Resulting Dataset

Our annotators analyzed around 800 sentences, discarding 200 of them, finally obtaining 600 *annotated items* in 5 languages. Due to a coverage issue of the Russian language in BabelNet, we retain only sentences tagged with nominal or verbal synsets. Dataset statistics are reported in Table 1.

As expected, we note that the lexicalizations found in \mathbb{B} have been substantially refined by our annotators in all languages, as reported in Table 2. Indeed, across languages, on average, 54% of the good lexicalizations have been added by our annotators, while 42% of the pre-existing lexicalizations have been removed. More importantly, given a language and two sentences containing words referring to the same synset, on average only in 55% of cases do they also share those words’ good lexicalizations, confirming that the assumption that

all synonyms of a word are valid replacements can lead to incorrect results.

These statistics lead us to a straightforward, but important, conclusion: only in a limited number of cases is a lexicalization belonging to a given synset to be considered as a suitable translation equivalent for the provided target word and its context. Examined jointly, these metrics suggest that relying on synset lexicalizations from BabelNet alone is prone to producing errors, either due to BabelNet’s intrinsic noise, or due to the lack of different granularity of synsets and contextualized words.

Sentences’ Properties Description As we stated in Section 3.2.1, the sentences we annotate are all usage examples of specific concepts obtained from WordNet or Wiktionary. Such examples are typically short main clauses with no subordinates, featuring on average 9 words (around 50 characters per sentence). All selected sentences include a semantic context which allows the meaning of the target word to be properly identified.

3.4 Analysis Procedure

DIBIMT’s analysis procedure is fairly simple: given an *annotated item* $X_L = (s, w_i, \sigma, \mathcal{G}_L, \mathcal{B}_L)$ and a translation model \mathcal{M} , we compute $t_L = \mathcal{M}_L(s)$, i.e., the translation of s in language L according to \mathcal{M} . Then, we use Stanza(Qi et al., 2020) to perform tokenization, part-of-speech tagging and lemmatization of t_L and, finally, we check if there is any match¹¹ between the lemmas of the translated sentence and those contained in \mathcal{G}_L or \mathcal{B}_L . In case there is no match, we mark the translation as a MISS; otherwise, we mark it as GOOD or BAD depending on which set matched the lemma.

This produces an *analyzed item*, which for simplicity we denote as $X_L^M = (X_L, t_L, R, \omega_L)$, where R is one of GOOD, BAD or MISS and ω_L represents the matched lemma in case there was a match (GOOD or BAD), ϵ otherwise.

4 Results and Discussion

We now: i) use DIBIMT to carry out an evaluation of 7 different machine translation systems; ii) report the obtained results, including a thorough statistical and linguistic evaluation; iii) extensively discuss our findings, providing multiple measures of semantic bias; and iv) offer some insights into

¹¹A more detailed description of the analysis procedure is provided in Appendix A.

the causes of such biases. In Appendix D we include a model-specific breakdown of the various scores and metrics reported throughout this section.

4.1 Comparison Systems

We test a wide range of models, both commercial and non-commercial ones, and report their performances on DIBIMT’s evaluation metrics:

- **DeepL Translator**¹², a state-of-the-art commercial NMT system.
- **Google Translate**¹³, arguably the most popular commercial NMT system.
- **OPUS** (Tiedemann and Thottingal, 2020), the smallest state-of-the-art NMT model available to date, a base Transformer (each model has approximately 74M parameters) trained on a single language pair on large amounts of data.
- **MBart50** (Tang et al., 2021), multilingual BART fine-tuned on the translation task for 50 languages (610M parameters). We refer to **MBart50** as the English-to-many model, and to **MBart50_{MTM}** as the many-to-many model.
- **M2M100** (Fan et al., 2021), a multilingual model able to translate from/to 100 languages. We test both versions of the model, the 418M parameter one (which we dub **M2M100**) and the 1.2B parameter one (dubbed **M2M100_{LG}**).

4.2 Discussion of MISS

Figure 2 reports general results of the analysis per (model, language) pair. Given the high percentage of *analyzed items* classified as MISS, we asked our annotators to perform an inspection on a random sample of 70 items per language in order to unearth the reasons, with varying results. We identified multiple causes, namely: i) word omission in the translation (around 19% of items, mostly in Chinese and Italian); ii) issues with Stanza’s tokenization (around 11%, mostly Chinese and Russian) and lemmatization (around 12%, mostly Italian and German); iii) words translated as themselves (approximately 5%, often in multilingual neural models); iv) translations which have nothing to

¹²<https://deepl.com/>

¹³<https://translate.google.com/>

	DeepL	Google	M2M100	M2M100 _{LG}	MBart50	MBart50 _{MTM}	OPUS	Mean
DE	74.60	21.90	22.19	26.96	28.73	28.65	27.99	33.00
ES	57.87	22.54	25.51	30.00	33.89	32.66	36.66	34.16
IT	53.49	18.04	21.83	25.14	29.34	30.54	29.95	29.76
RU	71.58	22.89	26.22	35.19	36.06	33.33	41.07	38.05
ZH	46.00	15.04	16.99	22.35	31.21	34.15	27.75	27.64
Mean	60.71	20.08	22.55	27.93	31.85	31.87	32.68	32.52

Table 3: General results: accuracy on DiBiMT across models and languages. Higher is better.

	DeepL		Google		M2M100		M2M100 _{LG}		MBart50		MBart50 _{MTM}		OPUS		Mean	
	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI	SFII	SPDI
DE	34.78	28.30	86.61	79.54	82.00	76.15	78.90	74.71	84.10	73.86	84.95	74.24	79.85	76.25	75.89	69.00
ES	56.04	46.14	83.84	78.41	83.08	77.95	79.87	73.84	77.13	71.06	79.06	71.57	74.85	69.12	76.27	69.73
IT	57.71	49.01	85.47	80.62	80.22	76.58	78.69	76.10	78.67	71.51	79.41	69.48	80.59	72.02	77.25	70.76
RU	41.97	33.64	84.01	83.49	79.85	78.34	74.72	69.69	73.86	70.11	78.58	72.87	68.49	69.27	71.64	68.20
ZH	64.97	59.58	91.97	87.98	91.81	87.18	88.79	82.17	80.39	73.14	76.59	71.50	79.96	75.66	82.07	76.75
Mean	51.10	43.33	86.38	82.01	83.39	79.24	80.19	75.30	78.83	71.94	79.72	71.93	76.75	72.46	76.62	70.89

Table 4: Semantic Biases: SFII, i.e., Sense Frequency Index Influence, represents the average percentage of errors at varying levels of $\mu_{\lambda_P}(\sigma)$. SPDI, i.e., Sense Polysemy Degree Importance, instead, represents the average percentage of errors at varying level of $\delta_L(\lambda_P)$. Lower is better.

do with the source text¹⁴ (around 23%); and v) missing terms from either \mathcal{B}_L (around 18%) or \mathcal{G}_L (around 11%). We intend to thoroughly investigate and tackle these issues and translation phenomena as future work.

4.3 General Results

Table 3 reports accuracy for non-MISS *analyzed items* (i.e., $\frac{\#GOOD}{\#GOOD+\#BAD}$). With the sole exception of DeepL, which greatly outperforms every other competitor, models achieve extremely low scores, in the range of 20%-33%. Surprisingly, Google Translate performs worst across languages.

4.4 Analyzing the Semantic Biases

In addition to accuracy, DiBiMT analyzes the semantic biases of a translation model via four novel metrics, which we define in detail in what follows.

Sense Frequency Index Influence (SFII) We study the sensitivity of models to disambiguating senses with respect to their frequency. To do this, we define $\mu_{\lambda_P}(\sigma)$ as the index of synset σ in $\Omega_{EN}(\lambda_P)$ ordered according to WordNet’s sense frequency, as computed from SemCor. That is, in-

¹⁴An example is the sentence *he is a crack shot*, where the word *shot* is translated by MBart50 into Italian as “schianto”, which can be interpreted in this case as “someone very good looking”.

dex k means that synset σ is the k -th most frequent meaning for λ_P .

In Figure 3(a), we plot the number and percentage of errors made on average by the models, grouping items by $\mu_{\lambda_P^X}(\sigma^X)$, where X is a non-MISS *analyzed item*. As expected, the less frequent a meaning for a given word is, the harder it is for the model to correctly disambiguate it.

Finally, given a (model, language) pair, we define the Sense Frequency Index Influence (SFII) as the average percentage of errors, for each group, that we detected. Values are reported in Table 4. Interestingly, DeepL proves once again to be the best, obtaining a score of 51%, far below the average 80% achieved by the other models, with most non-commercial models performing $\leq 80\%$.

Sense Polysemy Degree Importance (SPDI)

Similarly to SFII, we also study the extent to which the polysemy degree, i.e., how many senses a given word can have, impacts the models’ disambiguation capabilities. This experiment mirrors SFII, but groups items by their lemma’s polysemy degree $\delta_{EN}(\lambda_P^X)$ instead of μ . Figure 3(b) reports the results on all items. Unsurprisingly, similarly to the frequency index, we observe that higher polysemy leads to more errors, confirming that models still struggle with very polysemous words. Similarly to SFII, SPDI is defined as the average percentage of

	DeepL		Google		M2M100		M2M100 _{LG}		MBart50		MBart50 _{MTM}		OPUS		Mean	
	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+	MFS	MFS+
DE	53.68	84.21	56.76	86.82	61.28	87.23	59.13	87.30	58.89	89.72	55.82	89.56	56.98	87.92	57.51	87.54
ES	59.89	87.91	61.96	89.05	61.81	89.37	61.78	88.03	60.17	91.10	63.09	91.85	64.47	91.21	61.88	89.79
IT	68.08	86.38	61.96	87.23	60.75	86.79	62.82	88.81	62.90	87.50	68.97	91.81	64.48	89.66	64.28	88.31
RU	50.00	83.33	48.12	83.28	47.87	83.41	45.25	84.16	47.39	87.20	44.91	87.96	48.40	84.04	47.42	84.77
ZH	49.07	88.89	56.05	88.20	59.06	91.34	59.35	92.45	50.66	89.87	54.17	90.28	51.71	87.45	54.30	89.78
Mean	56.14	86.15	56.97	86.92	58.15	87.63	57.66	88.15	56.00	89.08	57.39	90.29	57.21	88.06	57.08	88.04

Table 5: Frequency Analysis: MFS represents the average percentage of times the model mistakenly translates the target word into a lexicalization belonging to the Most Frequent Sense associated with λ_P . MFS+, instead, checks whether the wrong translation belongs to any synset that is more frequent than the target one. Lower is better.

Figure 2: General results of the analysis. Numbers represent percentages of the whole dataset (600 items). A full-page version of this image, for readability purposes, is available in the Appendix (Figure 16).

errors at varying polysemy degrees, and its values are reported in Table 4: once again, DeepL outperforms all other systems by a large margin, confirming that it is the least biased across the board.

Most and More Frequent Senses To further corroborate our findings about semantic biases, we study how often models predict senses that are more frequent than the target one. Given a BAD analyzed item X_L^M , we denote $\hat{\sigma}$ as the synset associated with the wrongly translated lemma ω_L .¹⁵ Then, we check the frequency of σ and $\hat{\sigma}$ with respect to λ_P^X : if $\mu_{\lambda_P^X}(\hat{\sigma}) < \mu_{\lambda_P^X}(\sigma)$, then the system’s disambiguation steered towards a sense that is more frequent than the target one, which we

¹⁵In the case in which there are multiple possible synsets, we take the most frequent according to $\mu_{\lambda_P^X}$, as we need to rely on the assumption that the surface form represents the intrinsic disambiguation performed by the NMT system.

	ALL	NOUN	VERB
Accuracy	32.11	34.15	30.02
%MISS	38.03	29.36	47.57
MFS	57.86	60.13	52.60
MFS+	88.68	87.57	88.74
SFII	76.98	69.16	76.90
SPDI	70.80	66.86	72.87

Table 6: Results by PoS tag. Numbers represent the mean value of each score introduced in the paper. The column ALL summarizes the results reported in the other tables.

dub More Frequent Sense (MFS+); additionally, if $\mu_{\lambda_P^X}(\hat{\sigma}) = 1$, then the model disambiguated the source word w_i to the Most Frequent Sense (MFS) of the associated lemma λ_P^X . The results of both these analyses are reported in Table 5.

We can observe a few interesting results: first, on average, almost 60% of the time a mistake reflects the Most Frequent Sense of the target word (second-last column); second, almost 90% of the errors concern translations towards more frequent senses of the target word (last column). Importantly, these results are consistent across systems, whether commercial or not. Although it might seem straightforward, NMT models are still strongly biased towards senses that are more likely to be encountered during training; while this could be related to the pattern-matching nature of neural networks, it also depends heavily on the training data the model was trained upon, and this needs to be further investigated in future research.

4.5 Are verbs harder than nouns?

The existing literature in WSD points to the fact that verbs are generally harder than nouns, mostly due to their highly polysemous nature (Barba et al., 2021b). We try to analyze whether MT models

Figure 3: Overall distribution of errors, summed across all models and languages, with respect to (a) Sense Frequency Index ($\mu_{\lambda_P}(\sigma)$) and (b) Sense Polysemy Degree ($\delta_{EN}(\lambda_P)$). Red bars represent the number of errors (i.e., BAD items) for a given group, grey bars represent the number of correct (i.e., GOOD items) items. Orange lines represent the percentage of errors (i.e., $\frac{\#BAD}{\#GOOD+\#BAD}$) for a given group.

are affected by the same phenomenon: in Table 6, we report the average results obtained by running DIBIMT on all its sentences (column ALL) and the subset of sentences whose target word was either a NOUN or a VERB. In general, we observe an average drop of accuracy of 4 points, as well as an astounding difference of 18 percentage points in MISS handling, which we will investigate more thoroughly in future work. Interestingly, MT models are much more inclined to translate nouns into their most frequent sense; we attribute this difference to the generally higher polysemy of verbs compared to nouns, which increases the size of the space of possible translations for a given verb, thus decreasing the chance that it gets translated into the MFS. Aside from this, we draw the same conclusion as that drawn by previous works in the field of WSD, with nouns being generally easier to translate than verbs.

4.6 Is the encoder disambiguating?

We try to assess to what extent, in a multilingual encoder-decoder architecture, the encoder is determining the implicit disambiguation of the source sentence before generating the translation. For instance, we ask ourselves this question: given an ambiguous word w_i in the source sentence s , how often does the model translate it into a lexicalization representing the same sense, if prompted to translate s into different languages? Intuitively, if the encoder was the sole contributor to the implicit disambiguation performed by the model, we would expect to see the meaning to always be the same, regardless of the target language.

To measure this, we perform the following experiment: given a model \mathcal{M} ,¹⁶ two languages $L1$

¹⁶We disregard OPUS here as it is a set of bilingual models, rather than a single model capable of translating into multiple

Figure 4: Language Frequency Correlation: percentage of times that an item translates to the same synset.

and $L2$ and an *initial item* X , we take \mathcal{M} 's analyzed items $X_{L1}^{\mathcal{M}}$ and $X_{L2}^{\mathcal{M}17}$ and check if translations in $L1$ and $L2$ have a synset in common, i.e., $|\Omega_{L1}(\omega_{L1}) \cap \Omega_{L2}(\omega_{L2})| > 0$. The results of this experiment are reported in Figure 4.

We observe that, on average, this phenomenon occurs around 70% of the time. Hence, it is safe to assume that, while the encoder certainly plays an important role in the disambiguation of the input sentence, the decoder is also contributing significantly. Another interesting observation is that the alphabet of the target language does not seem

languages. We also disregard DeepL and Google Translate as their architecture is proprietary.

¹⁷We skip item X if either $X_{L1}^{\mathcal{M}}$ or $X_{L2}^{\mathcal{M}}$ is a MISS.

	DeepL	Google	M2M	M2M _{LG}	MB	MB _{MTM}	OPUS	Mean
DE	66.86	71.04	65.85	67.18	66.87	67.77	66.95	67.50
ES	67.89	72.76	66.77	66.86	65.37	67.18	66.83	67.67
IT	66.67	72.58	66.35	68.50	64.33	65.81	65.82	67.15
RU	66.76	69.55	66.42	67.69	66.35	64.29	69.21	67.18
ZH	68.42	71.89	69.26	69.82	68.93	69.58	69.88	69.68
Mean	67.32	71.56	66.93	68.01	66.37	66.93	67.74	67.84

Table 7: WSD Results: ESCHER’s accuracy on the set of English sentences of non-MISS *analyzed samples* for each (model, language) pair. Higher is better.

to have any influence, as language pairs involving Russian display scores that are very similar to those of the other three European languages. We attribute lower scores in Chinese to coverage issues in BabelNet, which would hinder a correct fulfillment of the condition defined for this experiment.

4.7 How challenging is DiBiMT?

Given the low performances achieved by MT models, we test a WSD system on the English sentences within DiBiMT, both to assess the toughness of our system and to establish an additional baseline. We use ESCHER¹⁸ (Barba et al., 2021a), a state-of-the-art model on English WSD. Interestingly, ESCHER achieves an overall accuracy score of 66.33, almost 15 points lower than the results on the standard WSD benchmark (80.7 on ALL, Raganato et al., 2017), therefore confirming the challenging nature of DiBiMT. Furthermore, in order to estimate the difference in disambiguation capability between NMT models and a dedicated WSD system, we compute ESCHER’s performances on the set of English sentences of non-MISS *analyzed items* for each (model, language) pair. We report these results in Table 7, whose accuracy scores can be directly compared to those in Table 3.

As expected, the average MT accuracy is significantly lower than ESCHER’s, with the sole exception of DeepL, which manages to surpass it on German and Russian. These results clearly demonstrate that current NMT models are still not on par with dedicated WSD systems, and thus that they might benefit from the inclusion of such WSD systems within the NMT ecosystem.

4.8 Is this a decoding issue?

As a final experiment, we assess whether the semantic biases are caused by search errors (i.e., failures of the decoding algorithm), or model errors (i.e., the models deemed their translations the

¹⁸The publicly available version trained on SemCor data only.

	M2M100	M2M100 _{LG}	MBart50	MBart50 _{MTM}	OPUS	Mean
DE	98.00	98.00	92.00	94.00	84.00	93.20
ES	100.00	98.00	88.00	90.00	94.00	94.00
IT	94.00	90.00	86.00	100.00	88.00	91.60
RU	94.00	90.00	98.00	92.00	88.00	92.40
ZH	96.00	98.00	94.00	98.00	92.00	95.60
Mean	96.40	94.80	91.60	94.80	89.20	93.36

Table 8: Model Errors: percentage of times a model thought its BAD translation was better than a GOOD one.

best possible). For each (model \mathcal{M} , language L) pair, we sample a BAD translation (t_{BAD}), pair it with a GOOD translation (t_{GOOD}) produced by another model (prioritizing DeepL), and ask annotators to check their correctness and apply corrections where needed,¹⁹ then compute the perplexities according to \mathcal{M} with the corresponding English sentence s , i.e., $p_{\text{GOOD}} = p_{\mathcal{M}}(t_{\text{GOOD}}|s)$ and $p_{\text{BAD}} = p_{\mathcal{M}}(t_{\text{BAD}}|s)$. We repeat this sampling 50 times per (\mathcal{M} , L) pair and check how often $p_{\text{BAD}} > p_{\text{GOOD}}$. Table 8 shows that, on average, this happens in 93% of cases, thus confirming that most semantic biases are embedded within models and are not caused by the decoding strategy.

5 Conclusions

In this work, we presented DiBiMT, a novel benchmark for measuring and understanding semantic biases in NMT, which goes beyond simple accuracy and provides novel metrics that summarize how biased NMT models are. We tested DiBiMT on 7 widely adopted NMT systems, extensively discussing their performances and providing novel insights into the possible causes and relations of semantic biases within NMT models.

Furthermore, statistics of our annotations suggest that, when dealing with translations, synsets’ lexicalizations cannot be used interchangeably, as their choice depends heavily on the context.

In the future, we plan to improve DiBiMT by introducing better heuristics to recognize and handle MISS cases, especially covering the linguistic phenomena we described (see Section 4.2); we also aim at widening language coverage and increasing the number of sentences in the benchmark, consequently improving word and sense coverage. To enable further research, we release DiBiMT as a closed benchmark with a public leaderboard at: <https://nlp.uniroma1.it/dibimt>.

¹⁹We do this to make the translations more grammatically fluent, and not to correct the disambiguation of the target term, which was never detected as being wrong in the sampled cases.

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A Analysis Procedure Details

Our analysis procedure, which we described in Section 3.4, involves steps that go beyond simple lemma matching. For instance, in case of multi-word expressions, we allowed annotators to specify a wildcard, i.e., any number of tokens (including zero) were allowed to expand and still trigger a match. Additionally, since Stanza has multi-word expansion tokenization for some of the languages in our list, when available, we try to perform matching on both the list of words (alongside the list of tokens) in the translated sentence. Finally, in case no match is produced by the aforementioned steps, we apply a surface-level string matching heuristic which, especially in Chinese, helps us increase coverage.

B Neural Models Implementation

We use HuggingFace’s Transformers library (Wolf et al., 2020) for all neural models. As per standard practice, we generate translations using beam search as decoding algorithm with beam size 5.

C Instructions for Dataset Annotation

In this work, we investigate semantic biases in Machine Translation across languages. You are provided with a spreadsheet containing 300 instances, each including the following information: a lemma, its part of speech, a definition and some good and bad translation candidates derived from BabelNet. Your task is to manually verify the correctness of the good candidates and add new good candidates if deemed necessary. Furthermore, you are asked to verify that all bad candidates are wrong.

From a translation perspective, a good candidate is a word which correctly translates the English target word in the given context. Instead, a bad candidate is a wrong translation of the English target word in the given context.

Please adopt the following guidelines while annotating:

- Do not annotate idioms.
- Do not annotate instances in which the semantic context does not allow us to unequivocally determine the meaning of the target word.
- Do not annotate proper names, e.g., “Run” in the sentence *The military campaign near that creek was known as “The battle of Bull **Run**”*.

- You are allowed to include cross-PoS candidates (that is, candidates whose PoS is different from that of the target word), in this case please include the candidate in square brackets like this:
`[candidate_with_different_pos|Px]`,
where x represents the part-of-speech tag of the translated word. Do this for multi-word expressions as well.

Mark with the tag “DISCUSS” difficult instances which you would like to discuss.

D Model-specific Analyses

We include model-specific analyses with per-language breakdown of the scores achieved on our benchmark. The column named ESCHER provides the scores of the WSD system on the subset of sentences of the specified model and language, and should be treated as an additional baseline to compare with the accuracy achieved by the system. Details can be found in Section 4.

- DeepL
- Google
- OPUS
- M2M100
- M2M100_{LG}
- MBart50
- MBart50_{MTM}

DeepL

Back to [Model-specific Analyses](#).

	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	36.07	74.60	53.68	84.21	28.30	34.78	66.86
ES	25.26	57.87	59.89	87.91	46.14	56.04	67.89
IT	20.21	53.49	68.08	86.38	49.01	57.71	66.67
RU	35.04	71.58	50.00	83.33	33.64	41.97	66.76
ZH	31.86	46.00	49.07	88.89	59.58	64.97	68.42
Mean	29.69	60.71	56.14	86.15	43.33	51.10	67.32

Figure 5: Evaluation on DeepL

Google

Back to [Model-specific Analyses](#).

	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	35.87	21.90	56.76	86.82	79.54	86.61	71.04
ES	23.29	22.54	61.96	89.05	78.41	83.84	72.76
IT	23.12	18.04	61.96	87.23	80.62	85.47	72.58
RU	35.37	22.89	48.12	83.28	83.49	84.01	69.55
ZH	32.49	15.04	56.05	88.20	87.98	91.97	71.89
Mean	30.03	20.08	56.97	86.92	82.01	86.38	71.56

Figure 6: Evaluation on Google

OPUS

Back to [Model-specific Analyses](#).

	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	37.84	27.99	56.98	87.92	76.25	79.85	66.95
ES	25.69	36.66	64.47	91.21	69.12	74.85	66.83
IT	29.11	29.95	64.48	89.66	72.02	80.59	65.82
RU	45.84	41.07	48.40	84.04	69.27	68.49	69.21
ZH	38.31	27.75	51.71	87.45	75.66	79.96	69.88
Mean	35.36	32.68	57.21	88.06	72.46	76.75	67.74

Figure 7: Evaluation on OPUS

M2M100

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	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	49.41	22.19	61.28	87.23	76.15	82.00	65.85
ES	41.91	25.51	61.81	89.37	77.95	83.08	66.77
IT	42.44	21.83	60.75	86.79	76.58	80.22	66.35
RU	51.77	26.22	47.87	83.41	78.34	79.85	66.42
ZH	48.66	16.99	59.06	91.34	87.18	91.81	69.26
Mean	46.84	22.55	58.15	87.63	79.24	83.39	66.93

Figure 8: Evaluation on M2M100

	DE	ES	IT	RU	ZH
DE	1.0	0.73	0.75	0.75	0.67
ES	0.73	1.0	0.79	0.73	0.70
IT	0.75	0.79	1.0	0.77	0.72
RU	0.75	0.73	0.77	1.0	0.61
ZH	0.67	0.70	0.72	0.61	1.0

Figure 9: Overall Language Cooccurrence Heatmap for M2M100

M2M100_{LG}

Back to [Model-specific Analyses](#).

	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	42.02	26.96	59.13	87.30	74.71	78.90	67.18
ES	36.75	30.00	61.78	88.03	73.84	79.87	66.86
IT	37.07	25.14	62.82	88.81	76.10	78.69	68.50
RU	42.50	35.19	45.25	84.16	69.69	74.72	67.69
ZH	39.73	22.35	59.35	92.45	82.17	88.79	69.82
Mean	39.61	27.93	57.66	88.15	75.30	80.19	68.01

Figure 10: Evaluation on M2M100_{LG}

	DE	ES	IT	RU	ZH
DE	1.0	0.72	0.78	0.71	0.68
ES	0.72	1.0	0.77	0.72	0.64
IT	0.78	0.77	1.0	0.73	0.73
RU	0.71	0.72	0.73	1.0	0.59
ZH	0.68	0.64	0.73	0.59	1.0

Figure 11: Overall Language Cooccurrence Heatmap for M2M100_{LG}

MBart50

Back to [Model-specific Analyses](#).

	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	40.24	28.73	58.89	89.72	73.86	84.10	66.87
ES	39.29	33.89	60.17	91.10	71.06	77.13	65.37
IT	40.10	29.34	62.90	87.50	71.51	78.67	64.33
RU	44.16	36.06	47.39	87.20	70.11	73.86	66.35
ZH	44.35	31.21	50.66	89.87	73.14	80.39	68.93
Mean	41.63	31.85	56.00	89.08	71.94	78.83	66.37

Figure 12: Evaluation on MBart50

	DE	ES	IT	RU	ZH
DE	1.0	0.68	0.68	0.65	0.58
ES	0.68	1.0	0.69	0.67	0.60
IT	0.68	0.69	1.0	0.73	0.61
RU	0.65	0.67	0.73	1.0	0.52
ZH	0.58	0.60	0.61	0.52	1.0

Figure 13: Overall Language Cooccurrence Heatmap for MBart50

MBart50_{MTM}

Back to [Model-specific Analyses](#).

	%MISS	Accuracy	MFS	MFS+	SPDI	SFII	ESCHER
DE	41.25	28.65	55.82	89.56	74.24	84.95	67.77
ES	41.06	32.66	63.09	91.85	71.57	79.06	67.18
IT	43.29	30.54	68.97	91.81	69.48	79.41	65.81
RU	45.18	33.33	44.91	87.96	72.87	78.58	64.29
ZH	44.59	34.15	54.17	90.28	71.50	76.59	69.58
Mean	43.07	31.87	57.39	90.29	71.93	79.72	66.93

Figure 14: Evaluation on MBart50_{MTM}

	DE	ES	IT	RU	ZH
DE	1.0	0.66	0.69	0.65	0.56
ES	0.66	1.0	0.73	0.72	0.60
IT	0.69	0.73	1.0	0.76	0.61
RU	0.65	0.72	0.76	1.0	0.54
ZH	0.56	0.60	0.61	0.54	1.0

Figure 15: Overall Language Cooccurrence Heatmap for MBart50_{MTM}

Figure 16: Full page version of Figure 2.

bn:00057755n	He poured a shot of whiskey.	
	A small drink of liquor.	
German	✓ Schlückchen Schuss	✗ Schlag Injektion
Spanish	✓ Trago Chupito	✗ Pistolero Tiro
Italian	✓ Goccio Bicchierino	✗ Iniezione Sparo
Russian	✓ шот рюмка	✗ стрелок выстрел
Chinese	✓ 杯 小杯	✗ 枪手 本垒打

Table 1: Example of item annotated in all languages. First row is the example, target word is in bold, second row is the definition of the synset associated with the word in the example.

bn:00036083n	They tracked him back toward the head of the stream.	
	The source of water from which a stream arises.	
German	✓ Flussursprung Quelle	✗ Kopf Kommando
Spanish	✓ Fuente Manantial	✗ Cabeza Jefe
Italian	✓ Fonte Sorgente	✗ Testa Capo
Russian	✓ исток	✗ проход вопрос
Chinese	✓ 源头	✗ 头 族长

Table 2: Example of item annotated in all languages. First row is the example, target word is in bold, second row is the definition of the synset associated with the word in the example.

bn:00094769v	<p>If you take off for Thanksgiving you must work Christmas and vice versa.</p> <p>To absent oneself from work or other responsibility, especially with permission.</p>	
German	<p>✓</p> <p>Sich eine Auszeit nehmen Sich freinehmen</p>	<p>✗</p> <p>Losgehen Starten</p>
Spanish	<p>✓</p> <p>Pedir un permiso Coger</p>	<p>✗</p> <p>Salir Llevar</p>
Italian	<p>✓</p> <p>Prendersi dei giorni Prendersi un permesso</p>	<p>✗</p> <p>Togliersi Decollare</p>
Russian	<p>✓</p> <p>брать выходной отдыхать</p>	<p>✗</p> <p>вычесть убить</p>
Chinese	<p>✓</p> <p>请假 休假</p>	<p>✗</p> <p>离开 减</p>

Table 3: Example of item annotated in all languages. First row is the example, target word is in bold, second row is the definition of the synset associated with the word in the example.